

Policy Brief

June 2024

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Dignity For Irregular Migrants at work in Farm to Fork Sectors (DignityFIRM)

1. Introduction

Farm to Fork (F2F) industries across Europe and beyond – harvesting fruit, processing it, preparing and delivering food to the consumers’ doorsteps – rely heavily on migrant workers. These workers may have experienced different migration trajectories and have different legal statuses. They may be mobile EU citizens, third country nationals with temporary residence or work permits, such as seasonal workers, or undocumented (irregular) migrants. Irrespective of their migration status, they have rights.

The recent farmers’ protests across the EU have led to policy proposals and initiatives seeking to reinforce the agri-food sector’s shorter-term resilience to crises, raising concerns, however, for their impact on environmental and social sustainability targets. Despite their vital role in the agri-food sector, (irregular) migrant workers, who often face poor and exploitative working conditions, have largely been overlooked.

The high systemic dependency on migrant workers coincides with persistent group vulnerabilities. Why do these F2F industries rely so heavily on vulnerable workers? Our choice for F2F labour markets is timely given the vital role of these industries for securing EU livelihoods. F2F labour markets offer the most evident example of how important migrant workers are for societies to provide in their basic needs. There is an urgency to address the deep structural contradictions between our societies’ formal exclusion of (irregular) migrant workers and their substantive role in the F2F labour markets. Especially now that the European Union (EU) and its Member States are embarking on one of the greatest transitions towards becoming sustainable and resilient societies.

The goal of the DignityFIRM project is to inform policy debates with analytical insights and contribute to better access to rights and services for migrant workers, including persons in an irregular status. At the same time the DignityFIRM project is addressing the well-being of the receiving communities, contributing to a more equitable and dignified future for F2F sector workers in the EU during the transition to sustainable F2F industries.

Three specific challenges addressed in this policy brief are:

- Measures that can contribute to ending violations of human rights along supply chains must be complemented with further measures targeted at protecting migrant workers;
- The regulatory infrastructure approach shows an urgent need to overcome policy silos to enable an integrated policy approach promoting dignified working conditions for migrant workers;
- The need for coordinated interaction between different actors and across borders in the interests of securing migrant worker rights and sustainable F2F industries.

To address these issues, this brief brings under the spotlight specific actions or policy issues that should be prioritised by EU policymakers in the next EU policy cycle.

2. Evidence and Analysis

The regulatory infrastructure approach developed by DignityFIRM shows an urgent need to overcome policy silos to enable an integrated policy approach promoting dignified working conditions for migrant workers, including those in an irregular situation. From an extensive policy analysis of regulatory infrastructure at play, it became clear that, in order to address the dynamics of irregularity and labour in F2F sectors, more than one policy field must be scrutinized.¹ Four policy fields are selected in this project (Migration, Social Rights, F2F Strategies, Corporate Social responsibility). The promotion of decent work and prevention of exploitation in the food supply chain requires **overcoming policy siloes** and taking further complementary actions in relevant policy fields. Among others, promoting corporate accountability, human rights and environmental due diligence standards for EU companies to ensure responsible business practices, should be ensured throughout the supply chain.

Analysis of Migration Policies

Three legislative instruments on migration policy have come to the fore in our preliminary analysis: the Return Directive 2008/115/EC, the Employer Sanctions Directive 2005/52/EC, and the recast Single Permit Directive 2024/1233/EU.

The EU Return Directive lays down common standards and procedures for returning irregular migrants. However, it does not provide any guidance on the treatment of migrants who cannot be returned, except for specifying that "their basic conditions of subsistence should be defined

¹Neidhardt, A.-H., Milazzo, E., Kapeti, L., Meeteren, M. van, & Lange, T. de. (2024). Dignity for (irregular) migrants employed in Farm to Fork Sectors: A Regulatory Infrastructure Approach to EU Legal and Policy Frameworks (3.1; Issue DignityFIRM Working Paper 3.1). <https://www.dignityfirm.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/Working-Paper.-Dignity-for-irregular-migrants-employed-in-Farm-to-Fork-Sectors.pdf>

according to national legislation". Return rates have remained low, thus creating a legal and policy vacuum for those who cannot or are not returned.

- Regularisations can be a solution to the vacuum left by the Return Directive, as regularisation offers irregular migrant workers a stronger framework of rights and services.
- Regularisations are, however, at the discretion of the EUMS to develop and the requirements set may (temporarily) increase migrant worker vulnerabilities.

There is a huge hypocrisy in a system that relies so heavily on migrant workers for keeping costs of food down and, at the same time, closes both eyes to the systemic abuse of their rights. To improve the governance of irregularities – in the realm of both labour and migration – actions are needed that can address the risk of exploitation of those who cannot be returned, and yet find themselves in an irregular situation.

However, said hypocrisy stretches further than the employment of non-returnable migrants. Legally staying and working TCN as well as EU mobile workers can be just as vulnerable at work in Farm2Fork sectors. Small enterprises at the end of a supply chain may also find themselves in a near to impossible position to deliver products without migrant labour and – when meaning to treat them well – experience a high strain to comply to market pressures.

The EU Employer Sanctions Directive obliges the Member States to impose proportionate sanctions on employers illegally employing illegally staying workers. Furthermore, it aims to oblige the EUMS to provide irregularly staying migrant workers some protection. The implementation of the Directive is being evaluated. The DignityFIRM research will be providing insights on its functioning on the ground which can feed into such instruments as a Green Book or Commission Guidelines to improve this Directive's implementation. Employer sanctions should be used a lot more than it is the case, with the latest violent death of an Indian farm worker in Italy being the latest reminder.

Those taking advantage of migrant worker vulnerability irrespective of their migration status, should be sanctioned. Sanctioning should be done in a way which does not penalise those migrants in an irregular situation. Proper enforcement, especially in cross-border situations, through expanding the mandate of the European Labour Authority is called for. In the case of non-cooperation or non-enforcement by Member States, the European Commission should develop adequate infringement strategies.

At the same time, it is necessary to address the drivers motivating migrants to embark on perilous journeys towards the EU. An important driver is the F2F industries' structural demand of workers. This brings us to the EU's commitment to strengthen legal migration pathways. Despite the promise of legal pathways, there are few (structural) legal pathways for low-waged migrant workers coming to the EU, facilitating intra-EU mobility or regularizing the status of those already

present in the EU. In the absence of structural and rights-based pathways, existing legal frameworks, such as the intra-EU posting of third country nationals in the context of the intra-EU provision of services, is being abused.

The EU Single Permit Directive recast does not provide a sound legal pathway, yet it simplifies access to a single permit for the purpose of work and residence. Furthermore, the risk of exploitative employment relations and the uncertainties over the right to change employers, have to some extent been addressed in the recent recast.² Now, to ensure the Single Permit Directive recast contributes to the improvement of migrant workers' rights, its proper transposition, implementation and enforcement is called for; to be monitored closely in the next policy cycle.

Analysis of European Pillar of Social Rights

Upholding the rule of law entails upholding (irregular) migrant workers' rights. This calls for continued attention for actions falling under the EPSR in the new EU policy cycle. The European Pillar of Social Rights (EPSR) sets out 20 principles to support fair and well-functioning labour markets as well as social protection and inclusion. Actions under the EPSR could in principle help improve working (and living) conditions for non-EU nationals, including (irregular) migrant workers. Even if not explicitly mentioned, and irrespective of their migration status, workers have rights. Reflecting this, and also the need to take multistakeholder actions, in January 2024, the European Commission, the Belgian Presidency of the Council of the EU, and European social partners signed the **Tripartite Declaration for a Thriving European Social Dialogue**. The Declaration seeks to promote, amongst others, commitments among social actors to address labour shortages, including attracting foreign workers, improving their working conditions, and promoting their integration. These calls should be acted upon in the next cycle explicitly considering the interests of (irregular) migrant workers.

Analysis of Farm to Fork Strategy

The EU F2F Strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system (F2F Strategy in short) launched by the European Commission in 2020 presented a comprehensive plan to address the challenges of producing and consuming food in a fair and sustainable way. Being a core component of the **European Green Deal**, it connected to the EU's ambition to define a sustainable and inclusive growth strategy that can improve people's health and quality of life, care for nature, and "leave no one behind". The EU has committed to redesigning food systems, putting them on a sustainable path. It is however not clear whether the strategy efficiently addresses food security bearing in mind the heavy reliance of the agricultural sector on migrant workforce.

² Discussed in the DignityFIRM Joint Webinar held on 22 December 2023 and more extensively by De Lange, T., & Falkenhain, M. (2023). Precarity prevented or reinforced? Migrants' right to change employers in the recast of the EU Single Permit Directive. *Frontiers in Sociology*, 8(1), <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsoc.2023.1267235>.

In the new policy cycle, measures addressing the needs of farmers -following from the farmers protests - and ensuring adequate protection for agricultural workers, including (irregular) migrant workers, will be indispensable to achieving sustainability and resilience of the food sector. These include the protection-sensitive enforcement of relevant labour standards, as well as efforts to address structural conditions in the sector leading to irregularity.³

Analysis of Corporate Social Responsibilities

In EU law Corporate Social Responsibilities (CSR) has emerged as a critical area to ensure that legal and policy gaps in respecting human rights are addressed. Some progress was made on this front in the 2019-2024 cycle, although much remains to be done to close regulatory gaps. Recent developments include the **Regulation on Banning Products Made Using Forced Labour**. The Regulation establishes shared investigative responsibilities between the Commission and national authorities, as well as digital tools for information exchange and cooperation. Guidelines and support measures by the Commission are also envisioned to facilitate compliance, with a specific focus on small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). While civil society organisations criticised the proposed Directive for not requiring the consultation and remediation of worker victims, this law has the potential to combat forced labour. In its implementation attention should be paid to how it can also benefit (irregular) migrant workers.

DignityFIRM produces quarterly newsletters with updates on this regulatory framework. Available online: www.dignityfirm.eu

To conclude, the insights provided by the regulatory infrastructure approach strongly suggest that no individual measure in any individual domain will suffice, in itself, to achieve dignified working conditions for (irregular) migrant workers. Put differently, in identifying the way forward, a reflection is needed on which would be the most effective way of addressing vulnerability across the different policy domains and Farm 2 Fork sectors examined.

Furthermore, there is a need for coordinated interaction between different actors and across borders in the interests of securing migrant worker rights and sustainable F2F industries. Earlier research findings show that there is a lack of coordinated interaction between different actors and across borders to protect the rights of migrant workers, especially those in an irregular situation, but also in the case of EU mobile workers in low-waged jobs in the Farm 2 Fork Sectors. Policies may not be enforced for reasons that include the lack of mandate, of resources, and differing perspectives of stakeholders. This needs addressing if the hypocrisy in a system that relies so heavily on migrant workers while at the same time closes both eyes to the systemic lack of protection of their rights is to change structurally.

³ This topic is discussed in a DignityFIRM Manifesto https://www.dignityfirm.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/DF_Manifesto_01_def.pdf

3. Policy Implications and Recommendations

As the research is ongoing, these policy implications and recommendations should not be taken for our final recommendations. In due course, the DignityFIRM project aims to identify best practices of dignified living and working conditions for migrant workers in the EU, and will draft further policy recommendations to strengthen such positive practices. The following must be considered a first account of recommendations for future actions and initiatives to be taken by relevant policymakers.

Overall, there is a need to address the challenges faced by (irregular) migrant workers in the EU in a comprehensive and holistic manner. By focusing on legal protections, sustainable practices, and corporate accountability, other than increased awareness, the recommendations included in this Policy Brief and those that will follow during the course of the project, aim to create a more just and equitable environment for all stakeholders involved in the F2F sectors.

Taking a regulatory infrastructure approach reveals that among the policy actions to be prioritised, it is key to strengthen legal protections and safeguard the rights and dignity of migrant workers, ensuring access to justice and protection from exploitation and abuse:

- This calls for investigating and addressing cases where the rights of migrant workers along with public safety and health of all workers in F2F sectors, are violated or at risk of violation. Effective implementation requires firewalls in place between labour inspectorates and immigration authorities. Lodging a complaint should not be hampered by (the fear of) forced return.
- This also entails avoiding normalizing a culture of exemption and holding Member States accountable for fulfilling their responsibilities.
- This calls for a coherent approach that transcends policy siloes, key for the incoming Commission. It also calls for a multistakeholder approach, involving all relevant actors, including migrant worker.
- Among others, an integrated approach requires strengthening both the support for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the F2F in fulfilling their obligations to comply with decent labour requirements, including under the newly adopted Regulation on Banning Products Made Using Forced Labour.

While the above recommendations point to possible ways in which the governance of irregularity can be improved, to the benefit of all actors concerned, and (irregular) migrant workers themselves, more profound initiatives may be needed to address the root causes of irregularity, particularly in those sectors that depend structurally on them. Further policy actions should be geared towards addressing their vulnerability at the intersection of identified policies and by making available dignified legal pathways and regularisations.

To this end, the following actions, among others, could be taken.

- Create legal pathways for low waged workers. Living up to the commitments taken in recent initiatives, including the New Pact on Migration and Asylum calls for expanding legal pathways into the EU, also for low-waged workers essential to the F2F sectors.
- Ensure timely and proper transposition and implementation of the Single Permit Directive.

Overall, there is a need to **raise awareness**. There is ample attention for climate sustainability of food production. Yet, the social sustainability of European food supply chains is often overlooked. At the EU and Member State level there is an urgent need to increase awareness and improve access to information for all stakeholders, employers, migrant workers, consumers etc. so that they can all play their part in providing decent work, fulfilling rights and protections and have access to fair produced food.

4. Project Identity

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ABOUT DignityFIRM

Towards becoming sustainable and resilient societies we must address the structural contradictions between our societies' exclusion of migrant workers and their substantive role in producing our food.

www.dignityfirm.eu

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